

Agro2Circular

D6.6 – Natural capital assessment of demonstrated solutions

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List of abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
CF	SEEA Central Framework
CICES	Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services
EA	SEEA Ecosystem Accounting
E-LCA	Environmental Life-Cycle Assessment
ESVD	Ecosystem Services Valuation Database
ES	Ecosystem Services
F&V	Fruit and Vegetables
LCC	Life-Cycle Costing
LULUCF	Land use, Land Use Change, and Forestry
NCA	Natural Capital Accounting
NPV	Net Present Value
PHBV	Polyhydroxyalkanoate-type polymer
SEEA	System of Integrated Environmental and Economic Accounting
SUT	Supply and Use tables
TEEB	The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity
UNSD	United Nations Statistics Division

Glossary

Ecosystem services: benefits supplied by the functions of ecosystems and received by humanity [4].

Life Cycle Assessment: LCA is defined by the ISO 14040 as the compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and the potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle.

Life Cycle Costing Assessment (LCC): assessment of all costs related to a product or service within its life cycle, from raw material extraction over production and use until disposal.

Net present value: value of an asset determined by estimating the stream of income expected to be earned in the future and then discounting the future income back to the present accounting period [4].

1. Executive summary

National Capital Accounting (NCA) is “*the use of a structured, rules-based framework to systematically measure and report on stocks of natural capital and flows of ecosystem services*” [1]. It is an effective approach to support companies and governments to organise and analyse information related to their dependencies and impacts on nature. This report describes the application of an NCA analysis to selected Demonstrators of the A2C project, in particular those related to the valorization and upcycling of agri-food organic waste (Demo 3, 4 and 5). By adopting an innovative approach which estimates the value of Ecosystem Services preserved by A2C processes, namely using waste in production processes in place of primary raw materials, the NCA provides a quantitative measure of the positive contribution of Circular Economy to sustainability.

The report is structured in the following sections beyond the introduction: 3. methodological framework, that presents all the relevant concepts underpinning the conceptual structure and describes the procedure; 4. application in the Murcia region, that reports measurements and metrics, connects them with the Agro2Circular specific Demos and provide a discussion of the main results; 5. conclusions, that summarize the significance of this analysis and how it fits into the overall project framework.

Results show that the extent of the estimated value of Ecosystem Services preserved in the Demos varies according to the amounts of processed waste and type of crops considered, ranging from 1,200€ per year to more than 15,000€ per year. A sensitivity analysis was conducted considering the upscaling of A2C technologies, and applying them to the volume of waste generated by A2C partner companies each year. The results show that the value of ES could range from 430,000€ for apple waste to 40 million € for lemon waste considering the valorisation of all their waste amounts.

The results of NCA provide useful insights for A2C partners to integrate their sustainability assessments with detailed information on Ecosystem Services positively impacted by their solutions, which can be leveraged and communicated effectively within their value propositions. Also, the NCA complements the LCA and eLCC results considering a deeper understanding of the relations between the Demonstrators and the local territory of Murcia, enabling a territorial perspective.

2. Introduction

The circular economy can be defined as a regenerative system in which materials are kept in use for as long as possible. Materials are recovered and regenerated at the end of their useful life, thus extracting maximum value from them. This approach aims to reduce waste, resource consumption and environmental impacts associated with traditional linear economic models. The concepts of recycling and upcycling represent two fundamental pillars of a circular economy. Recycling encompasses the collection and processing of materials that would otherwise be discarded as waste, with the objective of transforming them into new products. Upcycling, on the other hand, involves the transformation of materials or products into new products that offer enhanced value or quality. By adopting recycling and upcycling practices, businesses can effectively reduce waste and conserve natural resources.

The recycling and upcycling of biomass represents a pivotal step towards the establishment of a circular economy, as it serves to reduce waste and advance the sustainable management of resources. The recycling and upcycling of biomass for the generation of organic raw materials essential for production entails the conversion of organic waste materials, including agricultural waste and forestry residues, into valuable products such as biogas, compost, biomass pellets, bio-oil and bioplastics.

On the one hand, biomass is becoming an increasingly prominent green alternative to materials derived from fossil fuels [2]. The advantages of biomass are manifold. It is a renewable resource, meaning that it can be naturally replenished in a relatively short period of time. This is in contrast to fossil fuels, which are finite and take millions of years to form. Furthermore, biomass can be generated as an output of primary sector activities, including agriculture, forestry, and aquaculture; or alternatively, it can be derived from agricultural waste, forestry residues, algae, and aquatic plants, reducing pressure on landfills and the environment. Biomass generated as output by the primary sector may be a good solution from an energy transition perspective, but not a good solution from an overall green transition perspective because the transformation of natural ecosystems into intensive plantations (to generate as much

biomass as possible) has trade-offs. In fact, natural and semi-natural ecosystems can provide a range of services that support many human activities in many different ways.

If the biomass needed for production can be obtained through recycling and upcycling processes, the benefit is twofold:

1. A decrease of pressure in terms of waste generation;
2. An avoided impact on natural and semi-natural ecosystems because the additional raw organic material did not require a land use transformation.

Estimates of avoided impacts on land can be structured around an ecosystem services approach. The concept of ecosystem services encompasses the provision of natural resources and goes beyond this to consider, among other things, the role of nature in removing negative externalities caused by human activities and in protecting human settlements and economic assets from physical and biological threats. Techniques exist to assess ecosystem services in both physical and monetary terms and to account such measurements in a systematic and coherent way. The objective of this study is to develop a methodology for identifying where and how to integrate natural capital accounting, with a particular focus on ecosystem services accounting, within the broader circular economy framework. This methodology is concretely applied to the Agro2Circular Demonstrators related to the upcycling of agricultural Fruit&Vegetable (F&V) wastes in the Murcia region.

The structure of the report is in accordance with the following narrative. Within a broader circular economy framework it is important to:

- Identify and frame the role of life cycle material, which refers to the materials used in the production, use, and disposal of a product;
- Identify and frame how the life cycle material interacts with the ecosystems.

Information concerning both life cycle material and its interaction with the ecosystems can be framed systematically and in a way that is coherent with conventional economic accounts. Therefore, ecosystem services accounts can be built to quantify the interaction of the material life cycle with ecosystems, and in this case specifically to estimate the avoided transformation of current land use for the purpose of providing additional organic raw material for industrial processing.

3. Methodological framework

The use of natural capital accounts in the analysis of the circular economy requires the consideration of different basic concepts belonging to different fields of knowledge. The starting point, of course, remains the circular economy framework itself and the specific components that need to be considered when nature plays an active role. Then, the other key framework is the system of integrated accounts: there are indeed accounting mechanisms that need to be put in place to ensure overall consistency. Furthermore, within the broad concept of natural capital, the definition, meaning and role of ecosystem services need to be clarified to avoid misleading assessments.

3.1 The Circular Economy Conceptual Framework

A common definition of the circular economy is based on the following statements: the value of materials in the economy is maximised and maintained over time; the use of materials and their consumption is minimised; and the generation of waste in particular and negative environmental impacts in general are minimised and avoided where possible [3]. Based on this definition, the "value of materials in the economy" takes into account (i) economic efficiency, (ii) environmental effectiveness and (iii) social equity.

According to the conceptual framework developed by UNECE and OECD [3], the main features of the circular economy, combined with the pressure-state-response model used in environmental reporting and assessment, generate four components: (i) the material life cycle and the production and consumption functions of the economy, (ii) the interactions with the environment, (iii) the policies and (iv) the resulting socio-economic opportunities. The components to be considered when attempting to connect specifically circular economy with ecosystem services are the "material life cycle and value chain" and the "interaction with the environment".

As described in [3], the material life cycle and value chain is structured around three themes:

- Material basis and productivity of the economy – material input, consumption and accumulation;
- Management efficiency of materials and wastes – waste reduction, reuse, recycling;
- Interaction with trade and globalization – import and export of materials and wastes.

This is the component capable of capturing technical innovation through novel actions within a product's lifecycle.

As described in [3], the interaction with the environment is described into two themes:

- **Physical evolution of natural assets** – material extraction rates and changes in natural resource stocks, repletion ratios and regeneration rates for renewable resources;
- **Environmental and human health impacts** – discharge of pollutants and other residuals, impacts from material extraction, processing and end-of-life management on habitats and species.

This is the component capable of capturing the impacts and dependencies of the material life cycle on ecosystems. To consider ecosystems goes beyond the availability of natural resources.

Figure 1 identifies the main themes related to the interaction with the environment within a circular economy conceptual framework.

Figure 1: Elements from the Circular Economy conceptual framework to focus on (own elaboration based on UNECE-OECD [3])

Natural capital accounts can support both components of the circular economy in different ways, as explained in the following sub-section.

3.2 The System of integrated Environmental and Economic Accounting

The production of goods and services in the economy requires inputs from, and has impacts on, the natural environment. These impacts are the depletion of resources, the generation of waste that is returned to the environment and the role of the natural environment in providing resources, absorbing waste and generally maintaining a habitable world. A systematic and structured relationship between the environment and the economy is needed to quantify the impacts of economic activities on the environment and vice versa.

The objective of Natural Capital Accounts (NCA) is to provide information on the environment that consistently complements the conventional system of economic accounts. In 1993, the United Nations Statistics Division (UNSD) published the System of Integrated Environmental and Economic Accounting (SEEA) to provide a framework for accounting for stocks and flows of natural resources, emissions of pollutants and waste, and environmental and economic transactions. Since then, the international statistical community has developed and endorsed a number of processes leading to the adoption of two SEEA standards. The environmental-economic accounting approach described in SEEA organizes environmental and economic data using the accounting concepts, structures, rules and principles of the SNA.

The first SEEA standard is the Central Framework (SEEA CF) [4], which includes:

- environmental flows in physical terms, which include material inputs, products and residues between the environment and the economy and within the economy;
- stocks of environmental assets, which include natural resources (such as timber, fisheries and water) or energy assets and measure how they change over an accounting period due to economic activities and natural processes. They can be assessed in physical and monetary terms;
- economic activities related to the environment, expressed in monetary terms, such as expenditure on environmental protection and resource management, production of 'environmental goods and services', environmental taxes and subsidies, payments to and by government for environmental purposes.

The SEEA CF accounts are based on environmental data that can be collected from a variety of sources, such as emission inventories and water and energy statistics. The systematic collection of environmental data makes it possible to monitor trends over time.

When focusing on flow accounts related to the material life cycle, it is important to consider the natural resources flowing from ecosystems to the primary sector, and then the products generated by the primary sector, together with the wastes associated with the production activities (*Figure 2*).

Figure 2: Supply and Use tables from SEEA CF (circled in green) to SNA (own elaboration)

The second SEEA standard is Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA) [5] which includes:

- the ecosystem extent accounts report in physical terms the total area of each ecosystem, classified by type, within a specified area. They are structured as asset accounts and their measurement over time shows the changes in extent from one ecosystem type to another over the accounting period;

- the ecosystem condition accounts report in physical terms the ecosystem status, based on selected characteristics at specific points in time. They are structured as asset accounts and their measurement over time shows the changes to their condition and therefore the health status of ecosystems;
- the ecosystem services accounts report in both physical and monetary terms the ecosystem contribution generated by the ecosystems and allocated to economic units (economic sectors, government and households). They are flow accounts structured as Supply and Use tables;
- the ecosystem asset accounts in monetary terms aggregate ecosystem services by ecosystem types to report changes over time of ecosystem assets. Such changes may be negative (ecosystem degradation) or positive (ecosystem enhancement).

All accounts are spatially explicit (i.e. based on geo-referenced data). When focusing on ecosystem services that support socio-economic activities, SUT records the flows that ecosystems provide to the socio-economic system; such flows are eventually transformed by the socio-economic system into goods and services provided as intermediate consumption to economic sectors or as final consumption to government and households (*Figure 3*).

Ecosystem Services	Supply								Use	Economic Units				
	Cropland	Grassland	Woodland and forest	Wetlands	Heathland and shrub	Sparsely vegetated land	Rivers and lakes	Coastal		Primary sector	Secondary sector	Tertiary sector	Households	Global society
Biomass growth														
Pollination														
Carbon sequestration														
Pest control														
Water purification														
Flood control														
Soil retention														
...														

Figure 3: Supply and Use table of SEEA EA (own elaboration)

When ecosystems are altered, their ability to provide services changes. For example, woodlands and forests transformed into intensive monocultures will no longer be able to provide services such as flood control, carbon sequestration, soil retention, water purification and nature-based recreation. The annual provision of these services will be lost forever. Therefore, the impact on land cover and land use in terms of ecosystem transformation can be measured in terms of the services that ecosystems provide.

3.3 Identification, assessment and accounting of Ecosystem Services

Ecosystem services can be defined as the ecological contribution to human activities [6], [7], [8]. In the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES), they are grouped into three broad categories:

- **Provisioning services** - ecosystem contribution to any type of benefit to humans that can be extracted from nature, such as fisheries, timber, plants and medicinal benefits.
- **Regulating and maintenance services** - ecosystem contribution to everything that makes life possible for people, such as clean air and water, bacterial decomposition of waste, wild pollination, and mitigation of floods and erosion.
- **Cultural services** - ecosystem contribution to spiritual enrichment, cognitive development, reflection, recreation and aesthetic experiences.

The assessment of ecosystem services for accounting purposes is strongly linked to the way in which ecosystems provide services. Indeed, ecosystems may act as sources, sinks, buffers or means of transmitting information [9]. Furthermore, when acting as a source or sink, they may be subject to sustainability thresholds. Here are some examples:

- **Source:** ecosystems act as sources of matter and energy. When it is about “source-provision”, ecosystem generates mass and biomass that are eventually extracted. In case the extraction is above the regeneration rate of the natural resource, there will be a sustainability issue in terms of depletion. Examples are wood and fish provisions. When it is about “source-suitability”, ecosystem act as sources of matter and energy by providing suitable habitats and condition within the ecosystem to generate eventually matter and energy. In this case, there is no sustainability thresholds, but rather presence or absence of ecosystems able to provide services such as pollination, soil fertility, pest control.

- **Sink:** ecosystems act as sinks to store, immobilize or absorb matter. This type of ecosystem services applies to role of ecosystems in cleaning the negative externalities generated by human activities, such as pollution and wastes. When it is about “sink-absorption”, the emission of pollutants can be beyond the absorption rate and the overuse of these services may lead to ecosystem degradation. Examples are air filtration, water purification and soil decontamination. When it is about “sink-storage”, there is no sustainability threshold, but it is rather a matter of ecosystem presence of absence, like the case, for example, of forests to store carbon.
- **Buffer:** ecosystems act as transformers, changing the magnitude of flows of matter or energy. This is the case of services such as flood control, coastal protection, off-site soil retention. What matters is the presence or absence of ecosystems able to provide these services.
- **Information:** ecosystems deliver information, which does not modify their original state. This type refers to cultural services such as nature-based recreation and tourism, nature-based education, aesthetic and spiritual services. What matters is the presence or absence of ecosystems able to provide these services.

The role of ecosystem services in supporting socio-economic activities can be multifaceted [10]:

- they provide ecological inputs that affect directly the production process, like in the case of biomass provision and pollination;
- they remove negative externalities that are directly generated by the production process, like in the case of air filtration that cleans air emissions and water purification that cleans wastewater;
- they protect against a series of threats that indirectly affect production given the geographical location of relevant economic assets, like in the case of flood control (i.e. physical threats), pest control (i.e. biological threats), nature-based tourism (other threats);
- they guarantee compliance to overarching environmental targets, like in the case of climate change mitigation (e.g. carbon storage and sequestration services) and halting biodiversity loss (e.g. habitat and species maintenance)

Based on the way ecosystem services are provided and the role they play in supporting socio-economic activities, *Figure 4* summarizes how they match with the life cycle material and the interaction with ecosystems.

Figure 4: Ecosystem services features and the interaction of the material life cycle with ecosystems
(own elaboration)

3.4 Natural Capital Accounting and ecosystem services in the circular economy framework

From the previous subsections, it can be concluded that:

- (i) the advantages and disadvantages of alternative circular economy scenarios can be measured in terms of the material life cycle component and its interaction with the ecosystem;
- (ii) there is a coherent system to account for the interaction between ecosystems and socio-economic systems, which pass through ecosystem services;
- (iii) the impact on land cover and land use can be measured through the annual flow of the services provided by ecosystems.

The rationale behind the proposed methodology is based on the principle that in order to generate additional biomass to be supplied to the socio-economic system, we would need to transform land and thus alter ecosystems. However, if the additional biomass is generated through recycling activities, ecosystems are not altered and there is still an additional flow of biomass to be provided to the socio-economic system (*Figure 5*).

Figure 5: How to account for the benefits of recycled biomass using the ecosystem services SUT (own elaboration)

The biophysical assessment and monetary valuation of the ecosystem services provided by the land that is not converted to generate the additional biomass flow (generated instead by recycling activities) can be used as a proxy for the avoided negative interaction of production processes with ecosystems.

Based on the flow-chart example of one A2C Demonstrator, Figure 6 provides a visual summary of how sustainability in the agri-food industry can be quantified in terms of reduced pressure on waste generation (less waste to landfill) and increased amount of biomass to be used in manufacturing (more raw material in production).

MATERIAL LIFE CYCLE

Figure 6: The “material life cycle” box (own elaboration)

The natural resources involved in this process are water and energy. An increase or decrease in the amount of water or energy depends on how efficient the transformation process can be. The demand for these resources can, together with waste generation, have an impact on the environment. However, this is not the ecological interaction that will be studied and assessed.

The impact on the environment is accounted by considering the opportunity to offer additional biomass for manufacturing transformation without converting the current land uses. Economic processes need organic raw materials, which are not obtained by additional cultivated land, but rather from agri-wastes from current cultivated land. Ecosystems will not be modified and will be able to keep on generating the current flows of services that are assessed in physical and monetary terms (*Figure 7*).

There is an avoided negative impact on the land, which can be quantified together with the benefits of reducing the amount of waste sent to landfill. The accounting of ecosystem services will focus on monetary estimates of the flows that 'unchanged' ecosystems in Murcia will be able to provide to economic sectors and households.

3.5 Possible procedures to embed ecosystem services accounts in Agro2Circular scenarios

The ideal procedure to calculate the avoided land use transformation required to produce the additional tons of organic raw materials obtained through the recycling process would be to convert the LCA scenarios into corresponding hectares of land. Finally, the annual flow of ecosystem services per hectare is related to these equivalent hectares (

Figure 8).

Figure 8: The ideal procedure to compute the avoided land transformation (own elaboration)

On the other hand, there could be an alternative approach to estimate the number of hectares the project avoids being converted. This approach requires the application of the following formula (*Equation 1*):

$$\text{Land Area (km}^2\text{)} = \text{Total Biomass Needed (t)} / \text{Yield (t/km}^2\text{)}$$

Equation 1

The variable "Total Biomass Needed" is provided by the Agro2Circular Demos and represents the total organic raw biomass provided by the agricultural waste for the transformation process. The organic agri-food waste selected in the Agro2Circular project were citrus, artichoke, broccoli, cauliflower, grape and apple residues. These residues were selected on the basis of their composition (for having a high concentration of phenolic compounds of interest or fibre content) and for being predominant crops in the region of Murcia and other regions of Europe, which guarantees an adequate supply and a correct replication of the results to other regions [11]. In the NCA, the following agri-food waste are considered: lemon, artichokes, broccoli, apples, according to data availability and the Demos included in the assessment. In the case of artichokes, the raw organic biomass is provided by both the primary sector (production, collection and distribution) and the transformation sector (peels and waste). In the case of lemons and apples, the raw organic biomass is only provided by the transformation sector; in the case of broccoli, from the primary sector only. The biomass not provided by these F&V is not included in the estimate of equivalent km².

The variable "Yield" is expressed in tons per km² and represents the average agricultural yield of selected crops in the region per year.

Once the Land Area is computed, it is multiplied by the €/km²/year estimated for the selected ecosystem services in the region, after subtracting the value of the crop yield (*Equation 2*):

$$\text{Avoided land transformation (€)} = \text{Land Area (km}^2\text{)} * [(\text{€/km}^2 \text{ ES}) - (\text{€/km}^2 \text{ of crop yield})]$$

Equation 2

This procedure can be used to provide an initial estimate of the value of the avoided land transformation per year and eventually remain as a reference for validation in case the LCA conversion per hectare (or km²) is undertaken.

4. Application of the NCA methodological framework in the Murcia region

Different ecosystem services characterize different biogeographical regions due to differences in climate (temperature, precipitation and seasonality), soil and geology (nutrient availability, water retention and drainage), topography (elevation and slope), latitude (sunlight and daylight hours) and, of course, human activities that alter the natural composition.

Based on the characteristics of the Region of Murcia, ecosystem services are identified, assessed and valued for accounting purposes, so that they can be used as a proxy for the impact on the land in terms of transformation practices (as explained in the previous section).

4.1 Ecosystem services identification in the Murcia region

The Region of Murcia has a Mediterranean climate, with hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters. The main natural features of the Region of Murcia include several mountain ranges (including Sierra Espuña, Sierra de Ricote and Sierra de Carrascoy), a long coastline along the Mediterranean Sea (with sandy beaches, rocky coves and cliffs), the Segura River and its tributaries, which support riparian ecosystems and provide water for agriculture and human settlements; semi-arid ecosystems such as grasslands, scrubland and salt marshes; and several protected areas, such as the Sierra Espuña Nature Reserve, El Valle Regional Park and the Salinas y Arenales de San Pedro del Pinatar Nature Reserve. Based on the region's ecosystems and habitats, it is possible to identify a number of relevant ecosystem services, as listed in *Table 1*. The table lists together with ecosystem services, their priority for the study we need to undertake and the availability of datasets that it is possible to use. For example, although fire control is a critically important ecosystem service, there is no assessment and valuation available for the region of Murcia that we can use.

Therefore, only the ecosystem services that are highlighted in Table 1 are the ones that will be the subject of assessment, valuation and accounting in this study.

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	Division	Group	Class	Importance	Data availability
Provisioning	Biomass	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used for nutrition	High	Yes
		Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Fibres and other materials from wild plants for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials)	High	Yes
		Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used as a source of energy	High	Yes
	Genetic material from all biota	Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi	Seeds, spores and other plant materials collected for maintaining or establishing a population	Medium	No
		Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi	Higher and lower plants (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties	Medium	No
		Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi	Individual genes extracted from higher and lower plants for the design and construction of new biological entities	Medium	No
Regulating and maintenance	Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs to ecosystems	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Bio-remediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	High	No
		Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	High	No
		Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Smell reduction	Low	No
		Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Noise attenuation	Low	No
		Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Visual screening	Low	No
	Regulation of rivers	Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Control of erosion rates	High	Yes

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		Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Buffering and attenuation of mass movement	High	No
		Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control, and coastal protection)	High	No
		Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Wind protection	Low	No
		Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Fire protection	High	No
		Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Pollination (or 'gamete' dispersal in a marine context)	High	Yes
		Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Seed dispersal	Medium	No
		Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Maintaining nursery populations and habitats (Including gene pool protection)	High	No
		Pest and disease control	Pest control (including invasive species)	High	No
		Pest and disease control	Disease control	Medium	No
		Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere and oceans	High	Yes
		Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation of temperature and humidity, including ventilation and transpiration	High	No
Cultural	Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems	Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through active or immersive interactions	High	Yes
		Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable scientific investigation or the creation of traditional ecological knowledge	Medium	No
		Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable education and training	Medium	No

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	Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that are resonant in terms of culture or heritage	Medium	No
	Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable aesthetic experiences	Medium	No

Table 1: List of ecosystem services identified as relevant for the region of Murcia, Source: extracted and adapted from <https://cices.eu/resources/>

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4.2 Data collection process

4.2.1 Data on Ecosystem Services

The biophysical assessment of the six ecosystem services (including crop provision) is extracted through zonal statistics for the Murcia region from the following data catalogue made publicly available by the European Commission:

<https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset/d810c03e-535f-4f48-879e-ef26c7c61e24>

The assessment of each ecosystem service requires a specific technique, which can be relatively straightforward when raw data and statistics are available. The process may become more complex when a proxy must be created through the use of ecological modelling.

Based on *Table 1*, the following ecosystem services are extracted and described: agro biomass provision, soil retention, pollination, carbon sequestration, woody biomass provision, flood control and nature-based recreation.

First, the assessment of agro-biomass provision is based on Material Flow Accounts¹ and represents the yearly flow of the total harvested biomass (*Figure 9*). The reference year is 2021.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_mfa/default/table?lang=en&category=env.env_mrp

Figure 9: Agro-biomass provision service, used as reference layer

The information on crop provision is used to set a reference benchmark. The cultivation of crops would in fact be the land use destination if the area were to be converted.

Second, there is no data set that can be used for the assessment of pollination, nor is there any data set available for adaptation. Pollination is estimated using a biophysical model based on a combination of an expert-based model [12] and a species distribution model [13] to map the presence of habitats suitable to host wild pollinators (*Figure 10*).

Figure 10: Pollination service in the Murcia region

Changing land use will affect the availability of habitat suitable for hosting wild pollinators and thus the provision of pollinating services. It should be noted that the assessment of crop provision, which is used as a benchmark, already includes crop pollination as an ecological input. Consequently, these two services can be compared, but they cannot be aggregated in order to avoid double counting.

Third, there is no data set that can be used for the assessment of soil retention, nor is there any data set available for adaptation. This service concerns the process of holding or keeping soil in place to maintain soil quality, prevent erosion, and protect natural habitats.

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The estimation (*Figure 11*) is based on a biophysical model that employs the RUSLE equation [14], which serves as the foundation for a counterfactual model².

Figure 11: Soil retention service in the Murcia region

Should the land be converted to an alternative use, the current soil retention setting would inevitably undergo a significant change. It should be noted that the assessment of crop provision, which is used as a benchmark, already includes soil retention as an ecological input. Consequently, these two services can be compared, but they cannot be aggregated in order to avoid double counting.

² Ref. section 4.1 in

Fourth, the proxy used to assess carbon sequestration is the net carbon removals (*Figure 12*), which are based on LULUCF datasets³. The reference year is 2021.

Figure 12: Carbon sequestration service in the Murcia region

This assessment is closely linked to the woody biomass provision. In fact, this service flow would be lost if woodland and forest were converted into cropland.

³https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_air_gge/default/table?lang=en&category=env.env_air.e_nv_air_ai

Fifth, the assessment of woody biomass provision (*Figure 13*) considers the yearly flow of timber extraction from woodland and forests and is based on the forest resource accounts compiled by ESTAT⁴. The reference year is 2021.

Figure 13: Woody biomass provision in the Murcia region

If woodland and forest were converted into cropland, the service flow would be lost.

Sixth, there is no data set that can be used for the assessment of flood protection, nor is there any data set available for adaptation. The role of ecosystems to mitigate the risk of

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/for_vol_efa/default/table?lang=en&category=for.for_sfm

flooding is estimated through a biophysical model⁵ based on the curve number [15]. The reference year for the estimates used here is 2021.

Figure 14: Flood protection service in the Murcia region

The assessed level of protection depends mainly on the current presence of vegetation. The transformation of natural and semi-natural ecosystems into farmland would reduce the service flow.

The result in *Figure 14* is influenced by the fact that estimates used in the assessment are extracted from the model run on a European scale and refer to 2021. Furthermore, it is

⁵ Ref. section 6.1 in <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC116334>

possible that - following the floods of previous years (e.g. in 2016, 2019) - there have been improvements that have led to an increase in flood risk mitigation.

Finally, there is no data set that can be used, nor is there any data set available for adaptation for the assessment of nature-based recreation services that include both daily recreation and tourism. In terms of daily recreation, it is likely that users will be residents of the surrounding area. As a result, the number of residents can be used as a reference data source to estimate this component of the service. In the case of tourism, however, users are likely to come from a distance, making the number of nights spent in accommodation establishments a more appropriate reference data source to estimate this service. Nature-based recreation is estimated (*Figure 15*) using a biophysical model based on the Recreation Opportunity Spectrum [16] that maps not only the presence of natural features but also the human accessibility.

Figure 15: Recreation potential in the Murcia region

Land use is one of the key drivers in modelling the Recreation Opportunity Spectrum and its change will alter the provision of nature-based recreation.

4.2.2 Data on agricultural statistics

The agricultural statistics on yield/km² for lemon, artichokes, broccoli and apples for the Murcia region are extracted from the regional Statistical Portal (Portal Estadístico de la Region De Murcia), at:

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https://econet.carm.es/inicio/-/crem/sicrem/PU_datosBasicos/Indice1.html

Table 2 and Table 3 provide respectively the surface area of cultivated land for the selected crops (km²) and the yearly agricultural production (kg).

Surface area of cultivated land (km ²)				
Type of crop	2020	2021	2022	2023
Apples	0,74	0,60	0,66	0,66
Artichokes	56	63	59	49
Cauliflower and Broccoli	133	149	145	136
Lemon	257	262	270	267

Table 2: Evolution of the surface area of cultivated land according to type of crop (km²) (source: extraction from CARM <https://econet.carm.es/web/crem/inicio/-/crem/sicrem/PU590/sec21.html>)

Agricultural production (kg)			
Type of crop	2020	2021	2022
Apples	1.280.000	1.428.000	915.000
Artichokes	83.515.000	91.858.000	78.487.000
Broccoli	192.514.000	251.268.000	202.356.000
Lemon	640.588.000	648.288.000	546.460.000

Table 3: Evolution of agricultural production by type of crop (kg) (source: extraction from CARM <https://econet.carm.es/web/crem/inicio/-/crem/sicrem/PU590/sec21.html>)

4.2.3 Data on agri-food waste in the Murcia Region

Table 4, sourced from A2C Deliverable 1.4 "Residues management plan", describes the volume of waste generated per year in the Region of Murcia considering the F&V that have been targeted in the project, the specific parts or structures that make up the waste (skins, leaves, pulp, etc.), and the time of the year at which waste is generated.

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Crop	Waste	Amount (tonnes/year)	Collection
Apple	Pips, skins, cores and wasted raw material	1,200	From October to December
Broccoli	Stems and whole pieces of unsuitable raw material	41,400	All the year, but especially during autumn, winter and spring
Cauliflower	Leaves and stems	3,200	Especially in winter
Citrus fruit (lemon)	Peel and pulp	200,000	All the year
Artichoke	Bracts and stems	4,400	Especially from December to May
Grape	Stems and pieces of unsuitable raw material	24,275	From late summer to early winter

Table 4: Volume of waste generated per year in the region of Murcia (source: Deliverable 1.4 "Residues management plan")

In addition, Table 5 includes information about the company supplying each of the wastes and the volume of waste they generate per year:

Waste	Supplier	Amount (tonnes/year)
Apple	Agrotransformados (MCT) Laboratorios Almond (ALM)	350 - 400
Broccoli	ProExport (PROEXP)	33,400
Cauliflower	ProExport (PROEXP)	3,200
Lemon	Citromil (CITRO)	Pulp: 4,000 - 4,500 Peel: 30,000 - 40,000
Artichoke	ProExport (PROEXP)	3,000
Grape	Agrotransformados (MCT) Laboratorios Almond (ALM)	45 - 50

Table 5: Amount of waste supplied by companies (source: Deliverable 1.4 "Residues management plan")

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4.2.4 Data on Agro2Circular Demonstrators

Demonstrators 3, 4 and 5 have been selected for the Natural Capital Assessment in Task 6.4. A brief description of each Demo is provided below:

Demo 3: High added value substances from agri-food waste by green extraction + ultrasound

Figure 16: Demo 3 flowchart (Source: A2C project, Deliverable 1.9)

In Demo 3, whose flowchart is displayed in *Figure 16*, agri-food waste is processed through enzymatic extraction to obtain a solid and a liquid phase. The liquid phase, rich in sugars, is concentrated and sent to Demo 5.

The solid phase is purified through an oxidation treatment and dehydrated in an oven to produce a dry extract with a high fibre content.

The liquid phase is concentrated and purified using adsorption resins, and then freeze-dried to obtain an extract enriched in phenolic components.

Table 6 provides the quantity of biomass processed in Demo 3 per trial and in different scenarios: in a default scenario with current equipment and in an improved efficiency scenario, which could be potentially implemented always with the current equipment.

Description	Amount	Unit	Source
Quantity of biomass processed in Demo 3 per trial (lemon/artichoke/broccoli/apple waste)	150	kg	CTNC
Quantity of biomass potentially processed in default scenario with current equipment	1250	kg/year	CTNC
Quantity of biomass potentially processed in improved efficiency scenario with current equipment	7500	kg/year	CTNC

Table 6: Quantity of biomass processed in Demo 3 – different scenarios

Demo 4: High added value extracted substances from agri-food residues by green extraction + enzymatic hydrolysis assisted extraction + microwave

Figure 17: Demo 4 flowchart (Source: A2C project, Deliverable 1.9)

In Demo 4 (Figure 17), agri-food waste is processed through enzymatic extraction to obtain a solid and a liquid phase. The organic phase, rich in sugars, is concentrated and transferred to Demo 5.

The solid phase is purified using microwave-assisted extraction, resulting in a residual organic fraction, or it undergoes a purification and concentration process to obtain carotenoids, flavonoids, and polyphenols.

The liquid phase is subjected to centrifugation and ultrafiltration and then dehydrated in an oven, thereby obtaining dietary fibre. Simultaneously, the flavonoids recovered from

ultrafiltration are incorporated into the purification of the solid phase, where they are concentrated to obtain the carotenoids, flavonoids, and polyphenols mentioned earlier.

Table 7 provides the quantity of biomass processed in Demo 4 per trial and in different scenarios: in a default scenario with current equipment and in an improved efficiency scenario, which could be potentially implemented always with the current equipment.

Description	Amount	Unit	Source
Quantity of biomass processed in Demo 4 (lemon/artichoke waste) per trial	100	kg	DMC
Quantity of biomass potentially processed in default scenario with current equipment	1000	kg/year	DMC
Quantity of biomass potentially processed in improved scenario with current equipment	2000	kg/year	DMC

Table 7: Quantity of biomass processed in Demo 4 – different scenarios

Demo 5: Production of PHBV and carotenoids from fruit and vegetable waste

Figure 18: Demo 5 flowchart (Source: A2C project, Deliverable 1.9)

In Demonstrator 5 (Figure 18), the residues from Demonstrators 2, 3, and 4 undergo a fermentation process, followed by filtration and drying, with the aim of obtaining PHBV bioplastics and carotenoids.

The outcome provided by Demo 5 is reported in Figure 19 and shows that the total organic biomass needed to undertake the pilot experiment is 115,2 kg.

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Figure 19: – Biomass balance PHBV production (Source: CETECBIO)

Table 8 provides the quantity of biomass processed in Demo 5 per trial:

Description	Amount	Unit	Source
Quantity of biomass processed in Demo 5 (lemon waste) per trial	115,2	kg	CETECBIO
Quantity of biomass potentially processed in default scenario with current equipment	na	kg	
Quantity of biomass potentially processed in improved scenario with current equipment	na	Kg	

Table 8: Quantity of biomass processed in Demo 5 – different scenarios

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4.3 Ecosystem services assessment and valuation in the Murcia region

The rationale for this study is that land is not converted to produce additional agro-biomass, which is instead produced through recycling activities. Accordingly, it is essential to establish a benchmark estimate of the annual crop yield. The crop yield can be estimated in physical terms using the material flow accounts (ref. crop provision) and then translated into monetary terms using the agricultural economic accounts⁶. The regional average for both estimates are extracted for the year 2021 in Murcia and are reported in *Table 9*.

	tonne	Euro	km ²	euro/km ²
crop yield	2,402,309	571,645,209	11,261	50,764

Table 9: Crop yield in Murcia (year 2021) (Source: extracted and adapted from <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset/d810c03e-535f-4f48-879e-ef26c7c61e24>)

The current provision of ecosystem services in the Region of Murcia can be calculated as the sum of regional averages of annual flows (*Table 10*). The selected ecosystem services are: pollination, soil retention, carbon sequestration, woody biomass provision, flood control and nature-based tourism. The biophysical assessment of these services was briefly explained in the previous section. The outcomes of such assessment is translated in monetary terms as follows:

- **pollination:** the biophysical model generate tonne of crops that directly depend on wild pollinators. Monetary valuation is undertaken by adjusting the market price of pollinator-dependent crops⁴;
- **soil retention:** the biophysical model generates tonne of crops that directly depend on soil quality and fertility. The monetary valuation is based on replacement costs, specifically the cost of fertilizer for topsoil and the cost of bulk soil for non-topsoil components⁷;
- **carbon sequestration:** the LULUCF database provides tonne of carbon sequestered in vegetation, which is translated in monetary terms by using the carbon rate estimates annually available from the OECD reports [18];

⁶https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/apri_ap_crpouta/default/table?lang=en&category=agr.apri.apri_ap

⁷ Ref section 4.2 in <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC126566>

- **woody biomass provision:** the physical assessment (cubic meter of wood) based on ESTAT forest statistics are translated in monetary terms by using the forestry economic accounts⁸;
- **flood protection:** the biophysical model generates the number of hectares for which ecosystems mitigate the risk of flooding. The monetary valuation is based on the avoided damage cost, which also considers the presence of man-made flood protection infrastructure⁹;
- **nature-based tourism:** based on the number of overnight stays where the Recreation Opportunity Spectrum shows the medium and highest scores, the monetary valuation is carried out using benefit transfer unit values extracted from the EVDB.¹⁰

Table 10 shows the annual flow averages extracted for the region of Murcia in 2021:

Ecosystem services				
	<i>tonne</i>	<i>Euro</i>	<i>valuation technique</i>	<i>euro/km²</i>
Pollination	139,300	66,569,786	market price	5,908
Soil retention	23,337,272	29,702,132	replacement cost	4,981
Carbon sequestration	153,969	30,196,041	market price	2,682
	<i>cubic meter</i>			
Woody biomass provision	4,249,252	358,057,171	market price	31,787
	<i>hectare</i>			
Flood control	1,740	5,573,985	avoided damage	31,056
	<i>nbr of visits</i>			
Nature-based tourism	1,586,918	238,037,740	benefit transfer	21,139
Sum				97,552

Table 10: Ecosystem services in Murcia (year 2021) (Source: extracted and adapted from <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset/d810c03e-535f-4f48-879e-ef26c7c61e24>)

The average sum of €/km²/year of (only) six ecosystem services is almost double the average of crop yield reported in Table 9. Therefore, a land transformation aimed primarily at producing more agro-biomass would result in a loss of (97,552 – 50,764) = 46,800

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/for_emsuw/default/table?lang=en&category=for.for_eaf

⁹ Ref section 6.2 in <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC116334>

¹⁰ Ecosystem Services Valuation Database: <https://www.esvd.net/>

€/km²/year. This estimate, along with other key inputs, underpins the calculations presented in this study.

4.4 Application of the procedure to Demo 3, 4 and 5

The ecosystems of Murcia provide a range of annual services, as outlined in *Table 10*. The hypothesis adopted for this assessment is that the recycling of biomass residues allows for the provision of organic biomass to the production process without requiring the transformation of land to produce it. The transformation of land implies that the ecosystem services (ES) provided by land in its current status would be lost not only for one year, but for the entire life of the transformed ecosystems.

The formula that enables the capture of this lifespan assessment is the net present value (NPV), which requires the setting of two parameters: the discount rate and the lifetime.

The approach is undertaken through the following steps:

1. From the € 46,788/year/km² reported in par. 4.3, the NPV is processed using the discount rate (r) of 1% [17] and a lifetime (t) of 100 years [5], as follows:

$$\text{Ecosystem asset (€/km}^2\text{)} = \text{ES yearly flow} * ((1+r)^t - 1) / (r * (1+r)^t)$$

$$\text{Ecosystem asset (€/km}^2\text{)} = 46,788 * ((1+0.01)^{100} - 1) / (0.01 * (1+0.01)^{100}) = 2,949,018$$

Equation 3

This represents the average value per km² of ecosystem asset in Murcia for 2021.

2. From the agricultural statistics extracted for Murcia, the kg of agri-waste per km² are calculated and eventually divided by the yield (*Equation 4*).

$$\text{Land Area (km}^2\text{)} = \text{Total Biomass (kg)} / \text{Yield (kg/km}^2\text{)}$$

$$\text{Land Area (km}^2\text{)} = 1 / \text{Yield (t/km}^2\text{)}$$

Yield for different F&V:

$$\text{Yield}_{\text{lem}} (\text{kg}/\text{km}^2) = 2,473,815.16$$

$$\text{Yield}_{\text{art}} (\text{kg}/\text{km}^2) = 1,450,007.89$$

$$\text{Yield}_{\text{bro}} (\text{kg}/\text{km}^2) = 1,684,440.57$$

$$\text{Yield}_{\text{app}} (\text{kg}/\text{km}^2) = 2,380,000.00$$

Land calculation for each F&V:

$$\text{Land}_{\text{lem}} (\text{km}^2) = 0.0000004$$

$$\text{Land}_{\text{art}} (\text{km}^2) = 0.0000007$$

$$\text{Land}_{\text{bro}} (\text{km}^2) = 0.0000006$$

$$\text{Land}_{\text{app}} (\text{km}^2) = 0.0000006$$

Equation 4

These values represent the amount of km² needed in Murcia to generate respectively 1 kg of lemons, artichoke, broccoli and apples. Reference year is 2021.

3. The value of the ecosystem asset per km² that is preserved to avoid land transformation is calculated by multiplying the €/kg/km² per Land Area (km²) (*Equation 5*):

$$\text{Avoided impact on ecosystems} = \text{Ecosystem asset in } \text{€}/\text{kg}/\text{km}^2 * \text{Land Area in km}^2$$

$$\text{EV}_{\text{lem}} (\text{€}/\text{kg}/\text{km}^2) = 1.19$$

$$\text{EV}_{\text{art}} (\text{€}/\text{kg}/\text{km}^2) = 2.03$$

$$\text{EV}_{\text{bro}} (\text{€}/\text{kg}/\text{km}^2) = 1.75$$

$$\text{EV}_{\text{app}} (\text{€}/\text{kg}/\text{km}^2) = 1.24$$

Equation 5

This represents the value per 1 kg of organic biomass that ecosystems are still able to provide because they have not been transformed.

The specific case study concerns the organic waste from lemon, artichoke, broccoli and apple production, which is used as a raw material for the production of food, cosmetics and

nutraceuticals. The aim of this exercise is to address the issue of food waste and promote circular economy strategies to promote sustainability in the agri-food industry and reduce environmental impacts. Sustainability in the agri-food industry can come from the material life cycle component where waste is transformed into resources.

The monetary estimate expressed in terms of services generated by ecosystems is the following (*Equation 6*):

*Value of ES enabled by recycled biomass (€) = Recycled biomass (kg) * Ecosystem value enabled (€/kg/km²)*

Demo 3 – Lemon waste

ES value_lemon_demo (€) = 178.8

ES value_lemon_def scen (€) = 1,490.1

ES value_lemon_impr scen (€) = 8,940.7

Demo 3 – Artichoke waste

ES value_art_demo (€) = 305.1

ES value_art_def scen (€) = 2,542.2

ES value_art_impr scen (€) = 15,253.5

Demo 3 – Broccoli waste

ES value_bro_demo (€) = 262.6

ES value_bro_def scen (€) = 2,188.4

ES value_bro_impr scen (€) = 13,130.6

Demo 3 – Apple waste

ES value_app_demo (€) = 185.9

ES value_app_def scen (€) = 1,548.9

ES value_app_impr scen (€) = 9,293.1

Demo 4 – Lemon waste $ES\ value_lemon_demo\ (\text{€}) = 119.2$ $ES\ value_lemon_def\ scen\ (\text{€}) = 1,192.1$ $ES\ value_lemon_impr\ scen\ (\text{€}) = 2,384.2$

Demo 4 – Artichoke waste $ES\ value_art_demo\ (\text{€}) = 203.4$ $ES\ value_art_def\ scen\ (\text{€}) = 2,033.8$ $ES\ value_art_impr\ scen\ (\text{€}) = 4,067.6$

Demo 5 – Lemon waste $ES\ value_lemon_demo\ (\text{€}) = 137.3$

Equation 6

This represents the value of services that, thanks to this specific recycling process and based on the crop type that is valorized, could still be provided by ecosystems that do not need to be transformed in order to generate additional organic biomass.

It should be noted that the estimation of ecosystem services preserved by Demo 5 is provided only for information purposes. In fact, the waste processed in Demo 5 is constituted by residues coming from Demo 3 and 4, therefore considering related ES would generate a double-counting.

4.5 Sensitivity analysis and refinement

4.5.1 Sensitivity analysis

The monetary values obtained for ecosystem services enabled by A2C Demos single trials are influenced by the small scale of the Demonstrators and related upcycling processes, as

the quantities of waste processed in the Demo refers to rather limited waste quantities. Therefore two additional scenarios have been provided, based on the following data:

- quantity of biomass potentially processed in a year in a default scenario with current equipment, which served to calculate the ES in the “**Default scenario**”: *ES value_def scen*
- quantity of biomass potentially processed in improved scenario with current equipment, which served to calculate the ES in the “**Improved efficiency scenario**”: *ES value_impr scen*

These two scenarios show how the current equipment could treat higher amounts of agri-waste and thus lead to higher values of ES preserved thanks to the recycling process.

In order to perform a deeper sensitivity analysis considering the upscaling of A2C technologies, further calculations can be done by taking into account the volume of waste generated by A2C partner companies each year (*Table 5*). Related results of these calculations are provided below in *Table 11*:

Waste	Amount (kg/year)	ES value (€)	
<i>Apples</i>	350.000,00	ES value_partner apple waste =	433.679,12
<i>Artichoke</i>	3.000.000,00	ES value_partner artichoke waste =	6.101.383,34
<i>Broccoli</i>	33.400.000,00	ES value_partner broccoli waste =	58.474.726,20
<i>Lemon</i>	34.000.000,00	ES value_partner lemon waste =	40.531.165,69

Table 11: ES calculation considering all agri-waste produced by A2C partners

However, such waste amounts are not concretely treatable at the moment due to the fact that the processes have been developed within the A2C project and are not currently diffused. The current equipment could treat the quantities shown in the “improve efficiency scenario”. Nonetheless, the ES valuation considering the total volume of waste generated by A2C partners provides a scale of the potential value enabled by a relevant upscaling of these treatment and valorization processes.

Also, the result is influenced by the selection of the discount rate and lifetime values. Further sensitivity analyses could be conducted by varying these parameters.

4.5.2 Refinement

In order to refine the analysis, it could be interesting to value further costs or benefits that are generated by the use of waste and therefore avoided land consumption, instead of using primary raw materials.

Such further costs and benefits are discussed below:

- **Avoided costs of waste treatment:** using waste as a raw material for an upcycling process reduces the need to treat waste in other ways, and therefore could entail cost savings for the waste producers (avoided costs).

Currently, F&V waste in Murcia is mainly used as animal feed (see [19]), and therefore no costs for waste treatment can be envisaged.

- **Value of ecosystem services impacted by the A2C Demonstrators:** environmental impacts of A2C Demonstrators have been assessed within the LCA analysis (see [20]), and for selected Demos (Demo 3, 4 and 9) environmental externalities have been monetized in the environmental LCC (see [21]) and added to the conventional costs of Demos. However, LCA/LCC assess impact categories that can indirectly affect ecosystem services, but do not directly measure them as standalone outputs. Further developments of the LCA could better connect the impact categories with their potential effects on ecosystem services.

4.6 Discussion

The NCA analysis conducted for selected Demos in A2C has shown the value of ecosystem services that could be preserved by using agri-food waste into new productions processes, replacing primary raw materials. The extent of the estimated values varies according to the amounts of processed waste and type of crops considered, as summarized in *Table 12*:

Waste	Demo 3			Demo 4			Demo 5
	Trial	Default	Improved	Trial	Default	Improved	Trial
Apples	185.9	1,548.9	9,293.1				
Artichoke	305.1	2,542.2	15,253.5	203.4	2,033.8	4,067.6	
Broccoli	262.6	1,548.9	13,130.6				
Lemon	178.8	1,490.1	8,940.7	119.2	1,192.1	2,384.2	137.3

Table 12: Summary table of ES valuation from selected A2C Demos

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For these reasons, the most significant values are retrieved from Demo 3 due to the higher quantities of waste treated annually and types of crops treated.

This analysis provides added value for A2C project. ES valuation provides information that is not currently available nor taken into consideration by companies in the definition of their strategies and in the assessment of their overall sustainability. NCA starts from a national accounting system, but thanks to the use of spatial-explicit environmental economic information it can also be used at different geographical scales and aggregated or disaggregated where needed, adopting different territorial perspectives. In this sense, NCA enables to overcome a distinction between a micro (corporate) and a macro (government) perspective, reuniting them together.

Furthermore, NCA allows for more granularity in environmental assessment. At the moment ES assessment is not deepened within the LCA assessments, however given the increasing urgency to tackle ecosystem degradation, it is more urgent that ever to perform more detailed assessments on ES and include this information in decision-making.

Also, the approach used in the analysis, based on the value of preserved ES, is original and not previously attempted in other endeavors.

Finally, NCA relies on third-party data sources based on standards and approved procedures, providing companies with solid data to perform assessments [1].

Despite these points, the analysis is hampered by some limitations. Bio-physical models employed in the analysis are calibrated at European level, not specifically on the Murcia Region; as more data and models are available, it will be possible to further refine the analysis and calculations.

The approach used in this report, that considers avoided land transformation, is applied to the first step of the value chain, namely the one related to the provision of waste input to the overall process. All other impacts, i.e. waste treatment costs, transportation, are added in the other steps of the product value chain. It is therefore important to combine the NCA analysis with LCA and LCC analysis in order to obtain a comprehensive overview of the environmental as well as economic impacts across the value chain and its different steps.

5. Conclusions

The NCA presented in this report contributes directly to **Objective 2** of A2C project:

“Providing to the A2C technological solution the circular systemic approach by building a multidimensional model enabling the solution territorial deployment and its replication and scalability”, and in particular to points:

- i) develop and demonstrate the A2C circular business models;*
- iii) identify, analyse and quantify the territorial economic, social & environmental barriers/benefits and the relevant indicators.*

In fact, the results of NCA can be used by A2C partners to integrate their sustainability assessments with further insights into the Ecosystem Services positively impacted by their solutions, which can be leveraged and communicated effectively within their value propositions. Also, the NCA complements the LCA and eLCC results considering a deeper understanding of the relations between the Demonstrators and the local territory of Murcia, enabling a territorial perspective.

In this perspective, the results support the following scopes of the Work Programme:

2. “Demonstrate the role of the territorial circular economy to …” ; Increase resilience and provide concrete options for socio-economic..”Sustainability, **regeneration of ecosystems..”** ;

3 Address economic, social and environmental dimensions and include science, technology and governance components; demonstrate circular governance models and support the active participation of all relevant actors in each cluster; **prove the effectiveness and sustainability of circular business models.**

9. Include eco-design, industrial symbiosis and industrial ecology. **“Promote the role of ecosystems services …… and the use of natural capital accounting”**

By leveraging an original approach based on the value of preserved ES, the analysis aims to shed light on the contribution of circular economy to sustainability and integrate natural capital information effectively into the development and assessment of business strategies.

This deliverable develops a methodological framework for applying Natural Capital Accounting (NCA) to assess the performance of circular economy (CE) solutions—specifically those focused on organic waste valorization—through the lens of ecosystem services (ES).

The proposed methodology is designed to be scalable and adaptable to different territorial contexts, provided that appropriate input data and ecosystem modelling tools are available. The core principle underpinning this transferability lies in the structure of the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA) and its spatially explicit framework, which can be applied to any region where geo-referenced environmental and economic datasets exist. As described in the deliverable, two main system components are integrated in the proposed approach to apply NCA in CE contexts:

- **Material Life Cycle Analysis:** to track the input/output of biomass along the production chain to determine how circular practices (e.g., upcycling, recycling) reduce demand for primary resources.
- **Ecosystem Assessment:** to quantify the ecosystem services that would be lost if natural or semi-natural land were converted to produce additional raw biomass.

In order to implement the approach to other circular cases and regions, the following activities are suggested:

1. **Define the circular solution to be assessed and characterize it** (e.g. in terms of waste type and source, quantity processed and recycled annually, technologies used)
2. **Quantify the equivalent biomass demand** that would otherwise require land conversion
3. **Estimate the equivalent land area** that would be required to produce the same amount of recycled biomass from primary production
4. **Identify and value relevant ecosystem services** likely to be lost in case of land use change (e.g., pollination, soil retention, flood control, carbon sequestration, recreation), using available biophysical models and valuation techniques
5. **Calculate the value of preserved ES**, multiplying the avoided land area by the ES value per km².

Possible data sources include direct data provision from the partners involved in the implementation of the circular solution, local agricultural statistics (e.g., yield per hectare) from regional statistical offices, while ecosystem service data can be obtained from European or national repositories (e.g., EEA, JRC, national environment agencies). Many ecosystem services—such as pollination, soil retention, carbon sequestration—are modelled using standardized procedures.

Moreover, the **valuation phase** of ecosystem services is based on globally recognized methods—market price, replacement cost, benefit transfer—which can be calibrated to regional economic contexts. This flexibility allows the NCA to be customized while maintaining methodological consistency.

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6. Bibliography

- [1] J. C. Ingram *et al.*, 'Leveraging natural capital accounting to support businesses with nature-related risk assessments and disclosures', *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B*, vol. 379, no. 1903, p. 20220328, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.1098/rstb.2022.0328.
- [2] P. H. Egger and C. Keuschnigg, 'Resource dependence, recycling, and trade', *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, vol. 128, p. 103064, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jeem.2024.103064.
- [3] United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 'Guidelines for Measuring Circular Economy. Part A: Conceptual Framework Indicators and Measurement Framework', Palais de Nations, Genève; Switzerland. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://unece.org/statistics/publications/guidelines-measuring-circular-economy-part-conceptual-framework-indicators>
- [4] United Nations, European Commission, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, International Monetary Fund, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, The World Bank, 'System of Environmental-Economic Accounting 2012 Central Framework', Statistics Division, ST/ESA/STAT/Ser.F/109, 2014, [Online]. Available: https://seea.un.org/sites/seea.un.org/files/seea_cf_final_en.pdf
- [5] United Nations, 'System of Environmental Economic Accounting –Ecosystem Accounting', Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Statistics Division, ST/ESA/STAT/SER.F/124, Statistical Papers Series F No. 124, 2024, [Online]. Available: https://seea.un.org/sites/seea.un.org/files/documents/EA/seea_ea_f124_web_12dec24.pdf
- [6] R. S. De Groot, M. A. Wilson, and R. M. J. Boumans, 'A typology for the classification, description and valuation of ecosystem functions, goods and services', *Ecological Economics*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 393–408, Jun. 2002, doi: 10.1016/S0921-8009(02)00089-7.
- [7] TEEB, 'The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity - Ecological and Economic Foundations'. Edited by Pushpam Kumar, 2010, Earthscan: London and Washington

- [8] R. Haines-Young, M. Potschin, 'Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) V5.1 and Guidance on the Application of the Revised Structure'. Nottingham, UK. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://cices.eu/content/uploads/sites/8/2018/01/Guidance-V51-01012018.pdf>
- [9] A. La Notte, S. Vallecillo, A. Marques, J. Maes 'Beyond the economic boundaries to account for ecosystem services', *Ecosyst Serv* 35:116–129, Feb 2019. [Online] Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212041617307246>
- [10] European Commission – Joint Research Centre (2022), 'Linking accounts for ecosystem Services and Benefits to the Economy THrough bridging (LISBETH) Part II', EUR 31185 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC130438>
- [11] Agro2Circular Project, 'A2C Residues Management Plan', Deliverable 1.4.
- [12] G. Zulian, J. Maes, and M. Paracchini, 'Linking Land Cover Data and Crop Yields for Mapping and Assessment of Pollination Services in Europe', *Land*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 472–492, Sep. 2013, doi: 10.3390/land2030472.
- [13] C. Polce *et al.*, 'Species Distribution Models for Crop Pollination: A Modelling Framework Applied to Great Britain', *PLoS ONE*, vol. 8, no. 10, p. e76308, Oct. 2013, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0076308.
- [14] K.G. Renard, G.R. Foster, G.A. Weesies, and J.P. Porter, 'RUSLE: Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation'. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 46, 30-33, Jan-Feb 1991. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tucson.ars.ag.gov/unit/publications/pdffiles/775.pdf>
- [15] M. Huang, J. Gallichand, Z. Wang, and M. Goulet, 'A modification to the Soil Conservation Service curve number method for steep slopes in the Loess Plateau of China', *Hydrological Processes*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 579–589, 2006, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.5925>.
- [16] G. Zulian and A. La Notte, 'How to account for nature-based tourism in Europe. An operational proposal', *OE*, vol. 7, p. e89312, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.3897/oneeco.7.e89312.

- [17] R. Costanza, I. Kubiszewski, N. Stoeckl, and T. Kompas, 'Pluralistic discounting recognizing different capital contributions: An example estimating the net present value of global ecosystem services', *Ecological Economics*, vol. 183, p. 106961, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.106961>.
- [18] OECD, *Effective Carbon Rates 2021: Pricing Carbon Emissions through Taxes and Emissions Trading*. in OECD Series on Carbon Pricing and Energy Taxation. OECD, 2021. doi: 10.1787/0e8e24f5-en.
- [19] Agro2Circular Project, 'A2C business cases', Deliverable 6.5.
- [20] Agro2Circular Project, 'Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring (Final)', Deliverable D7.7
- [21] Agro2Circular Project, 'Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Final)', Deliverable D7.9.

